

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

Professional Recognition Scheme – Review of Professional Activities

Name: Gabi	Surname: Witthaus	
I confirm that all parts of this submission are my own work.	Signature: G.R. Witthaus	Date: 4 December 2020

<p>Applying for UKPSF Descriptor 3</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Descriptor 3: Senior Fellow (D3)</p> <p>Demonstrates a thorough understanding of effective approaches to teaching and learning support as a key contribution to high quality student learning. Individuals should be able to provide evidence of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. Successful engagement across all five Areas of Activity II. Appropriate knowledge and understanding across all aspects of Core Knowledge III. A commitment to all the Professional Values IV. Successful engagement in appropriate teaching practices related to the Areas of Activity V. Successful incorporation of subject and pedagogic research and/or scholarship within the above activities, as part of an integrated approach to academic practice VI. Successful engagement in continuing professional development in relation to teaching, learning, assessment, scholarship and, as appropriate, related academic or professional practices VII. Successful co-ordination, support, supervision, management and/ or mentoring of others (whether individuals and/or teams) in relation to teaching and learning* <p>*Please note that D3.VII is a distinctive characteristic of a claim for Senior Fellowship and evidence of this requirement should be pervasive throughout your application. Whilst not every example included needs to make reference to criteria D3.VII please remember that there does need to be evidence of sustained effectiveness in relation to this criteria across your submission.</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

<p><i>Submission requirement</i></p>	<p><i>All Areas of Activity, Professional Values and Core Knowledge.</i> <i>D3.7: Successful co-ordination, support, supervision, management and/or mentoring of others in relation to teaching and learning.</i></p>
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This element of your submission gives you the opportunity to review the way in which you teach and support learning. You should critically discuss your practice and consider the impact of any personal and professional development in the table below. It is important that you map Core Knowledge and Professional Values against your supporting narratives. You may wish to annotate these within your narrative as well as cross referencing them in the right hand columns.

Please consider what you have achieved in relation to a range of perspectives including:

a) your students; b) your colleagues / School / College; c) the University, your professional association or other organisation; d) national and/or international trends.

You should include recent examples from your higher education practice to illustrate your thorough understanding of effective approaches to teaching and learning support: what types of activity have you been involved in, what approach have you taken and why? How have you developed your understanding of teaching and supporting learning as a result and what are your next related steps?

Please start by giving a brief background to your current practice in the introductory section. This might involve an explanation of your role and responsibilities and the context in which you work.

PLEASE NOTE: Submissions in excess of the word counts will not be reviewed and will be returned to applicants to edit. This may mean that you miss the opportunity to have your application assessed.

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

<p>Introduction to your claim for Fellowship</p> <p><i>Use the box on the right to tell us about the context in which you currently work and appropriate background information, including an explanation of your role and responsibilities.</i></p> <p><i>Include how your values and teaching philosophy inform your teaching and/or learning support.</i></p>	<p>Supporting Narrative (up to a maximum of 300 words)</p> <p>I started my career working in community-based adult education in South Africa in the 80s, driven by the desire to create a more socially just society, inspired by Freire (1970). My work since then has always been informed by my belief in education as a common good, and by my commitment to encouraging critical thinking and learner agency. From 2005 to 2009, I became an early adopter of online learning, studying online for a Master’s in Training and Development through USQ (Australia). This was a life-changing experience for me, as I worked on real-world projects (such as creating educational websites) with fellow students around the world. It sparked my love of online education, and led me to move into higher education as a career.</p> <p>In 2009, I began working as a Teaching Fellow and Research Associate in learning technologies at the University of Leicester. Here I co-facilitated “Carpe Diem” workshops to help academics design and review their modules. In 2015 I took up a position as Learning and Teaching Facilitator at Loughborough University, which involved leading a community of teaching practice for academics.</p> <p>I joined UoB in February 2018 as an Instructional Design Consultant in the HEFi Digital Education (CAL) team. My role is to support and advise academics in relation to online and blended learning design and teaching. I run workshops/ webinars, mentor academics, and curate resources, combining the Carpe Diem and the communities of practice models. I emphasise critical reflection and inclusivity as core values, and try to inspire colleagues to do the same. This year, I have played a leadership role in conceiving and creating the learning and teaching “hub,” CAL TALKS (CAL Teaching, Assessment and Learning Knowledge Sharing), which facilitates practitioner-led support for academics in designing for, and delivering, remote teaching.</p> <p>Max word count: 300; Your word count: 295</p> <p>Reference</p> <p>Freire, P. (1970). <i>Pedagogy of the Oppressed</i>. New York: Herder & Herder.</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

Areas of Activity	Supporting Narrative 500 – 700 words per area of activity with a maximum total of 3,500 words.	Core Knowledge (K1-6)	Professional Values (V1-4)
<p>A1. Design and plan learning activities and/or programmes of study</p>	<p>In my role, I not only design and plan my own workshops for academics, but also advise and guide academics to design their own modules based on the scholarship of learning and teaching [D3VII].</p> <p>Learning design principles underpinning my CPD workshops for academics</p> <p>I have helped numerous programme and module teams to design or redesign their courses, mainly by running variations of the “Carpe Diem” workshop (Salmon and Wright, 2014), and using the ABCD process (see Section A5). These activities contribute to institutional quality enhancement, in that they involve “taking deliberate steps to bring about continual improvement in the effectiveness of the learning experience of students” (QAA Scotland, 2017). I guide academics through a process that includes: reviewing the module learning outcome statements and assessments; developing a storyboard to visualise the students’ pathway through the content that shows the alignment between learning activities, outcomes and assessment (Biggs, 2011); and designing learning activities to “scaffold” the learning (Vygotsky, 1978) [D3VII].</p> <p>My approach is based on the following key principles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I recommend that academics carry out learning design in a team in order to benefit from the different perspectives and experiences of their colleagues (Salmon & Wright, 2014). By encouraging dialogue in workshops, I have often seen an initially resistant workshop participant become more engaged as they share their own frustrations and concerns and hear what has worked for their colleagues and [D3VII]. I teach academics to create visual representations (e.g., storyboards, course maps and learning activity profiles) of their learning design (Conole, 2014; Cross, 	<p>K6</p> <p>K2,K3</p> <p>K3</p>	<p>V3</p> <p>V1</p> <p>V3</p>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>Galley, Brasher & Weller, 2012; Galley, 2015), in order to provoke critical reflection. Many academics experience “Aha” moments as they gain a holistic overview of how the elements of their course mesh together, and they see the highlights and the gaps in the learner’s journey [D3VII].</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In recognition of the pressures that academics face in terms of research and administrative duties, in addition to their teaching commitments, I help academics save time. For example, I show them how to create audio/ video materials that can easily be edited for future iterations of the module, and by helping them to manage students’ expectations. Academics greatly appreciate this awareness of their workload, and I have found that it can result in a complete turnaround in attitudes towards learning design from colleagues who were previously reluctant to invest time participating in workshops or webinars [D3VII]. <p>Impact of my curriculum design support for academics at D3VII level - examples</p> <p><i>Online MA TESOL and Applied Linguistics (University of Leicester)</i></p> <p>While working at the University of Leicester (2009 to 2014), I was a Teaching Fellow on the Online MA in TESOL and Applied Linguistics and a Research Associate in the Beyond Distance Research Alliance. I leveraged this combination of roles to influence the development of the online MA TESOL programme. I led a series of Carpe Diem workshops for the module leaders, which led the programme team to introduce discussion board based “e-tivities” (Salmon, 2013) for formative assessment [D3VII]. A subsequent evaluation found that the e-tivities had transformed the learning experience for students, making the programme more engaging and contributing to deeper learning.</p> <p><i>Translation Studies at UoB</i></p> <p>In November 2018, I ran a Carpe Diem workshop for the Department of Translation Studies, in order to support the programme team to design two new versions of an existing module - one for their distance learning programme and one for their campus-</p>	<p>K1, K2</p> <p>K3, K4</p> <p>K2, K3</p> <p>K2, K3</p>	<p>V1</p> <p>V4</p> <p>V3</p> <p>V1</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>based programme. The impact of this process was recently described by the programme director, Prof. Emma Tyler, as follows:</p> <p>“Gabi influenced the redesign of our MA in a fundamental way by organising a one-day carpe diem workshop for the programme team, focusing on the design of activities and learning outcomes, and supporting us in storyboarding the first module. The principles introduced in this session have guided the team’s development of the programme ever since. The blended nature of the new programme, which serves campus and distance cohorts simultaneously have also been informed by the one-to-ones I have had with Gabi. The new programme is hugely successful, an enormous improvement on our previous one, and very well received so far (introduced in October 2020).” [D3VII].</p> <p>Max word count: 700; Your word count: 691</p> <p>References:</p> <p>Conole, G. (2014). The 7Cs of Learning Design – a new approach to rethinking design practice. In S. Bayne, C. Jones, M. de Laat, T. Ryberg, & C. Sinclair (Eds.), <i>Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Networked Learning</i> (pp. 502–509). http://www.networkedlearningconference.org.uk/abstracts/pdf/conole.pdf</p> <p>Cross, S., Galley, R., Brasher, A., & Weller, M. (2012). <i>OULDI-JISC Project Evaluation Report: The impact of new curriculum design tools and approaches on institutional process and design cultures</i>. Milton Keynes: Open University. http://oro.open.ac.uk/34140/</p> <p>Galley, R. (2015). Learning Design at The Open University: Introducing methods for enhancing curriculum innovation and quality (pp. 1–20). Milton Keynes: Institute of Educational Technology, Open University. http://www.open.ac.uk/iet/learning-design/learning-design-ou</p>	<p>K4</p>	<p>V2</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>QAA Scotland. (2017). <i>Enhancement-Led Institutional Review Handbook</i> (4th edition). QAA Scotland. https://www.qaa.ac.uk/scotland/reviewing-higher-education-in-scotland/enhancement-led-institutional-review/handbook-and-guidance</p> <p>Salmon, G. (2013). <i>E-tivities: The key to active online learning</i>. London: Routledge. (2nd ed.).</p> <p>Salmon, G., & Wright, P. (2014). Transforming Future Teaching through ‘Carpe Diem’ Learning Design. <i>Education Sciences</i>, 4(1), 52–63. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci4010052</p> <p>Vygotsky, L. (1978). <i>Mind in Society</i>. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.</p>		
<p>A2. Teach and/or support learning</p>	<p>My experience of teaching in HE has included both academic and academic support roles, although primarily the latter. I discuss both below, starting with my experience in an academic role, as it has informed my approach to supporting academics who teach.</p> <p>Teaching PG students</p> <p>While at the University of Leicester (UoL) (2009-2014), I was an academic tutor and an “e-moderator” (Salmon, 2011) on the online Master’s in TESOL and Applied Linguistics. As a tutor, I supported tutees through to successful completion of the programme by providing individual academic support. As an e-moderator, I designed and facilitated online learning activities. This experience underpins my practice in working with academics today, as it gives me an “insider’s view” of teaching online.</p> <p>Next, I discuss how my role in providing CPD for academics has had an impact on curriculum design and delivery [D3VII].</p> <p>Leading institutional CPD programmes for academics at D3VII level</p> <p><i>The SPEED project – leading a CPD programme for five UK HEIs</i></p>	<p>K1</p> <p>K2, K3, K4</p>	<p>V1</p> <p>V3</p>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>At UoL I also led a JISC-funded project called ‘Sharing Practice for Embedding E-design and Delivery’ (SPEED)¹. SPEED aimed to disseminate and embed benefits from previous projects to four other UK universities. All five partner institutions wanted to enhance the quality of their teaching by providing CPD for academics in technology-enhanced learning. As project leader, I designed an online course which was intended to be delivered largely asynchronously over 12 weeks. I also set up synchronous webinars, where participants could engage in informal dialogue across institutions. In practice, only a few participants engaged fully in the asynchronous activities; however, there was great enthusiasm for the webinars. I therefore shifted the focus away from the asynchronous activities and added more webinars. At the end of the project, SPEED was judged to be a success, as participants indicated that they had gained practical skills that they could apply in their teaching [D3VII]. A few examples of the impact follow (from the SPEED blog²):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At Liverpool John Moores University, new templates were developed, tested and used in an online course which was offered to all LJMU academic staff as part of CPD development [D3VII]. - At the University of Derby, the SPEED resources were adapted for use in their Technology-Enhanced Learning training package for staff [D3VII]. - A participant from the University of Northampton noted: “SPEED made me revisit learning development activities already well-established at UoN and introduce different approaches to these activities. This work has provided me with a more flexible approach, and initial reaction ... is positive from colleagues.” [D3VII]. <p>SPEED confirmed my understanding that many academics find an informal community of practice more engaging than a “course” (Arthur, 2016).</p>	<p>K1, K2, K3 K6 K4 K2 K5 K4 K4</p>	<p>V3 V1 V1</p>
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¹ <https://www2.le.ac.uk/departments/beyond-distance-research-alliance/projects/speed>

² <https://speedprojectblog.wordpress.com/>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p><i>One-to-one mentoring of academics and colleagues</i></p> <p>I have also always provided one-to-one mentoring for academics and other colleagues. According to my ex-line manager from the University of Leicester, Prof. Alejandro Armellini: "During our time at the University of Leicester, Gabi's positive influence on individuals and teams was evident... Always generous with her time, Gabi was also a reference point, especially for junior colleagues, in relation to mentoring and other forms of support, which she was always willing to offer [D3VII]."</p> <p>According to Dr Keith Pond, my ex-line manager from Loughborough University: "Part of Gabi's role was ... to provide one-to-one mentoring with academic staff, particularly in the area of module and assessment design. In 'Champions' projects, where academic staff members were supported in adding new instructional techniques and digital assets to their teaching, she mentored numerous staff and helped their projects come to fruition." [D3VII]."</p> <p><i>Workshops, webinars and microCPD at UoB</i></p> <p>I have led several workshops and webinars for HEFi. Evaluations have always been highly positive [D3VII]. Some feedback received from participants follows:</p> <p>"Dear Gabi, I attended two of your brilliant events this week and found them so very useful. Thank you so much! I genuinely do now feel somewhat less daunted by the challenges ahead." [D3VII]."</p> <p>"Gabi ... advises 'encouraging students to respond to one another'. My approach has always been to reply to each student on an asynchronous discussion board. I can see that this limits student interaction and learning. I will change my approach in the future following Gabi's advice." [D3VII]."</p> <p>Max word count: 700; Your word count: 696</p>	<p>K1</p> <p>K1</p> <p>K2, K3</p> <p>K4</p> <p>K1</p> <p>K2</p>	<p>V1</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>References</p> <p>Arthur, L. (2016). Communities of practice in higher education: Professional learning in an academic career. <i>International Journal for Academic Development</i>, 1–12. https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2015.1127813</p> <p>Cox, M. D. (2013). The impact of communities of practice in support of early-career academics. <i>International Journal for Academic Development</i>, 18(1), 18–30. https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2011.599600</p> <p>Rienties, B., & Toetenel, L. (2016). The impact of learning design on student behaviour, satisfaction and performance: A cross-institutional comparison across 151 modules. <i>Computers in Human Behavior</i>, 60, 333–341. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.02.074</p> <p>Salmon, G. (2011). <i>E-Moderating: The Key to Online Teaching and Learning</i> (3rd ed.). Abingdon: Routledge.</p> <p>Witthaus, G. (2015). Storyboarding Resources. [Website]. <i>Art of E-Learning</i>. https://artofelearning.org/resources/storyboarding/</p>		
<p>A3. Assess and give feedback to learners</p>	<p>My experience of assessing and giving feedback to learners spans four main areas: I have marked students' work; I regularly give informal feedback to distance students on their assignment outlines; I give feedback to journal authors via peer reviews; and I support academics in designing for assessment in their modules. Each of these areas is outlined below.</p> <p>Marking and marking standardisation</p> <p>While working at the University of Leicester as a Teaching Fellow on the MA TESOL and Applied Linguistics, I was also a marker on this programme and participated in annual Marking Standardisation events, which were aimed at ensuring consistency of marking as</p>	<p>K2, K3</p>	

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>part of institutional quality assurance. My realisation that academics could have vastly differing interpretations of a student’s performance has led me to emphasise the importance of clear, consistent messaging to students about what “counts” as appropriate performance when I work with academics on assessment design [D3VII].</p> <p>Giving feedback to distance learners</p> <p>In my current role as a PhD researcher, I regularly provide academic support to the Master’s students around the world, in reciprocation for their participation in my research. The students are refugees who have received Sanctuary Scholarships (fee waivers) for online study. The subject is not my area of expertise; however, as these students are all from non-English speaking backgrounds and generally also from non-Western academic backgrounds, I am able to support them with many aspects of UK academic discourse and conventions. I also give them feedback on their assignment outlines and draft assignments, following the principles of dialogic feedback (Nicol & MacFarlane, 2006), which aims “to help students develop the ability to monitor, evaluate and regulate their own learning” (Nicol, 2010, p. 504). Audio feedback (usually via WhatsApp recordings) works well with these students, as it enables a dialogue to take place between us over a few days, allowing time for reflection. In this situation, I am applying learning from a research study I carried out with colleagues at the University of Leicester, where we found that audio feedback had a positive impact on students and tutors alike (Hawkridge, Armellini, Nie, Witthaus & Padilla Rodriguez, 2012). One Sanctuary Scholar, who has received higher marks for each successive assignment submitted over the last two years, has attributed his progress, in part, to the guidance he has received from me.</p> <p>Giving feedback as a reviewer/ editor</p> <p>I am a regular double-blind reviewer for various journals, including <i>IRRODL</i>, <i>Open Praxis</i>, and the <i>Journal of Interactive Media in Education (JIME)</i>. All these journals have an ethos of development and support for contributors, and so I always make an effort in this work to give clear and actionable feedback to authors. I have received positive feedback from journal editors who have recognised these efforts, for example, the IRRODL editor recently thanked me for my “insightful review”, and added: “I am sure your responses will</p>	<p>K5, K6</p> <p>K2, K3</p> <p>K1, K2</p> <p>K4</p> <p>K5</p> <p>K2</p> <p>K1</p>	<p>V3</p> <p>V1, V2</p> <p>V3</p> <p>V3, V4</p> <p>V1</p> <p>V4</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>be of value to the authors and of course to IRRODL. Your detailed comments and helpful points regarding how to structure the literature review will definitely help the authors to improve their writing.” Because these journals are widely read, my reviews play a role in enhancing the quality of teaching in the HE sector [D3VII].</p> <p>I am also currently co-editing a Special Edition of the journal, <i>Distance Education</i>, on “Reimagining Assessment in Online and Distributed Learning”³, for publication in April 2021. As an editor, I provide the first response to authors on their draft papers, which are on the topic of innovative practices in online assessment. My feedback to them focuses as much on their perceptions and reported experiences of assessment design as it does on the quality of their papers –potentially influencing assessment practices of the authors before publication, and of readers thereafter [D3VII].</p> <p>Supporting academics with assessment design</p> <p>My role has always included supporting academics in designing assessments and using learning technologies effectively for assessment. In an example from UoB, as the editor of the HEFi Gateway Module on Online Marking in 2018, I reviewed it from a pedagogical perspective and found that certain topics (e.g. using rubrics) were hard to follow. I created a storyboard proposing a complete restructure⁴, which influenced colleagues involved in the subsequent redevelopment of the module [D3VII].</p> <p>Max word count: 700; Your word count: 700</p> <p>References</p> <p>Hawkridge, D., Armellini, A., Nie, M., Witthaus, G. & Padilla Rodriguez, B. C. (2012). Digital audio for asynchronous interactive learning in curriculum design at an English</p>	<p>K1, K2</p> <p>K4 K2</p>	<p>V3</p>
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³ https://think.taylorandfrancis.com/special_issues/re-imagining-assessment-learning/

⁴ <http://linoit.com/users/Learningdesign/canvases/OSAF%20Gateway>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>university. Book chapter in Jia, J. (Ed.) <i>Educational stages and interactive learning: from kindergarten to workplace training</i> (pp. 468-484). Hershey, PA: IGI Global.</p> <p>Nicol, D. (2010). From monologue to dialogue: Improving written feedback processes in mass higher education. <i>Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education</i>, 35(5), 501–517. https://doi.org/10.1080/02602931003786559</p> <p>Nicol, D. J., & Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006). Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: A model and seven principles of good feedback practice. <i>Studies in Higher Education</i>, 31(2), 199–218. https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070600572090</p>		
<p>A4. Develop effective learning environments and approaches to student support and guidance</p>	<p>In this section, I outline my strategy for devising and leading CPD programmes for academics in relation to their teaching, which is built on the work I did at Loughborough University (2015-2017) in leading a community of practice, and incorporates the “Carpe Diem” model from my work at the University of Leicester (2009-2012).</p> <p>A central part of my role at Loughborough University was to lead the School of Business and Economics’ “Teaching Forum”, a community of practice for academics that met monthly to discuss their teaching practice. In communities of practice, workplace learning is seen as taking place more effectively in “situated” contexts through informal knowledge sharing between professionals than through formal training (Lave and Wenger, 1991). . There is a substantial body of literature on communities of practice for academics in HE (e.g. Arthur, 2016; Cox, 2013; Furco & Moely, 2012; Golden, 2016; Herbers et al., 2011, McDonald et al., 2008; Sánchez-Cardona, Sánchez-Lugo, & Vžlez-González, 2012). There is some criticism of the use of communities of practice in HE – for example, Annala & Mäkinen (2016) found that academics were not always willing to spend time trying to find common ground or to reconsider traditional practices. However, most of the literature contains positive findings from such initiatives. The key reported benefits of communities of practice are that they provide a safe, collegial space for learning, and that they allow early-career academics to learn from their more experienced colleagues (and vice versa, since younger academics are often more willing to experiment with new learning</p>	<p>K2, K3</p> <p>K1</p>	<p>V3</p> <p>V4</p> <p>V1</p>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>technologies), and these benefits tend to influence the promotion of new teaching practices.</p> <p>My role as facilitator of the Teaching Forum involved planning, designing and delivering monthly workshops for academics. I invited academics, and occasionally external speakers, to speak on panels, facilitated the workshops and curated all the associated resources in a site on the university's VLE, and regularly surveyed participants for feedback on the sessions and suggestions for future workshop themes. Workshop topics included teaching large cohorts, implementing blended and flipped learning, designing inclusive assessment, and student feedback literacy. The latter topic was particularly important to address in response to the business school's accreditation partners, who required evidence of student engagement with feedback as part of the quality assurance process. I designed these workshops following the Carpe Diem principles of learning design (Salmon & Wright, 2014), which emphasised a team-based approach to the sharing of practice, and providing situated, authentic learning opportunities for staff as a model for how to design learning for their own students [D3VII].</p> <p>In planning and facilitating the workshops, I worked closely with two academics who had received funding to lead three of these sessions over the course of a year, through having won an institutional teaching award that recognised their own good teaching practice. These sessions were particularly successful, with participant evaluations indicating significant levels of engagement [D3VII]. The key lesson for me from this experience was that the value of my pedagogical expertise was amplified by collaborating with academics who had a reputation as "good teachers" among their peers; by working together, we were able to have a greater impact on teaching practices - and ultimately on enhancing the quality of students' learning experiences, than I could have had alone. I subsequently co-authored a paper with these two colleagues, sharing our findings (Wilson, Wilson & Witthaus, 2020), which confirmed the benefits of communities of practice as an effective way of providing CPD for academics, and investigated aspects related to the demographics of participation. Collaboration with academics, especially in the form of facilitating practitioner-led knowledge sharing, became a cornerstone of my approach to leadership in all my CPD roles thereafter [D3VII].</p>	<p>K4</p> <p>K5</p> <p>K6</p> <p>K3</p> <p>K6</p> <p>K1</p> <p>K3</p> <p>K1</p>	<p>V4</p> <p>V3</p> <p>V3</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>Since coming to UoB, I have applied the principles of communities of practice and Carpe Diem in many different ways, the highlights being the Birmingham Digital Exchange (BDx) project, the Pedagogy for Engaging Distance Learners (PEDL) programme, and the CAL TALKS platform. These are all described in Case Study 1, which includes evidence of my leadership in, and the impact of, these initiatives [D3VII].</p> <p>Max word count: 700; Your word count: 674</p> <p>References</p> <p>Annala, J., & Mäkinen, M. (2016). Communities of practice in higher education: Contradictory narratives of a university-wide curriculum reform. <i>Studies in Higher Education</i>, 1–17. https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2015.1125877</p> <p>Arthur, L. (2016). Communities of practice in higher education: Professional learning in an academic career. <i>International Journal for Academic Development</i>, 1–12. https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2015.1127813</p> <p>Cox, M. D. (2013). The impact of communities of practice in support of early-career academics. <i>International Journal for Academic Development</i>, 18(1), 18–30. https://doi.org/10.1080/1360144X.2011.599600</p> <p>Furco, A., & Moely, B. E. (2012). Using Learning Communities to Build Faculty Support for Pedagogical Innovation: A Multi-Campus Study. <i>The Journal of Higher Education</i>, 83(1), 128–153. https://doi.org/10.1353/jhe.2012.0006</p> <p>Golden, J. E. (2016). Supporting online faculty through communities of practice: Finding the faculty voice. <i>Innovations in Education and Teaching International</i>, 3297(1), 84–93. https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2014.910129</p>		
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>Herbers, M. S., Antelo, A., Etting, D., & Buck, M. A. (2011). Improving Teaching Through A Community of Practice. <i>Journal of Transformative Education</i>, 9(2), 89–108. https://doi.org/10.1177/1541344611430688</p> <p>Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). <i>Situated Learning: Legitimate Peripheral Participation</i> (1st Edition). Cambridge University Press.</p> <p>McDonald, J., Collins, P., Hingst, R., Kimmins, L., Lynch, B., & Star, C. (2008). Community learning: Members' stories about their academic community of practice, in <i>Engaging Communities</i>. Engaging Communities; 31st HERDSA Annual Conference, March 2016, 10.</p> <p>Salmon, G., & Wright, P. (2014). Transforming Future Teaching through 'Carpe Diem' Learning Design. <i>Education Sciences</i>, 4(1), 52–63. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci4010052</p> <p>Sánchez-Cardona, I., Sánchez-Lugo, J., & Vžlez-González, J. (2012). Exploring the Potential of Communities of Practice for Learning and Collaboration in a Higher Education Context. <i>Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences</i>, 46, 1820–1825. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.05.385</p> <p>Wilson, A., Wilson, C. & Witthaus, G. (2020). Using a Community of Practice in Higher Education: Understanding the Demographics of Participation and Impact on Teaching. <i>International Journal of Teaching & Learning in Higher Education</i>. 32(1), pp. 39-48. Available at: http://www.isetl.org/ijtlhe/past2.cfm?v=32&i=1.</p>		
<p>A5. Incorporate subject and pedagogic research and/or scholarship within your professional practice as a teacher / supporter of learning.</p>	<p>Below, I provide examples of the ways in which I have based my teaching and support of academics on pedagogic research and encouraged academics to use a scholarly approach in their own pedagogy. Through the combination of research, publication, policy discussions and workshops with academics, I have informed practice and modelled a scholarly approach to the use of educational technology.</p>	<p>K1</p>	

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>Lecture capture</p> <p>While working at Loughborough University, I helped the Centre for Academic Practice (CAP) to review and update the university's lecture capture policy [D3VII]. Together with the Director of CAP, I conducted a literature review into the uses of lecture capture in HE (Witthaus & Robinson, 2016). A key finding was that lecture capture was a highly enabling learning tool, particularly for students with learning disabilities and those who spoke languages other than English. The review was subsequently referred to in a Times Higher Education article (McKie, 2018), and it was used to inform a case study in a business education context, which was published (Pond, Lambert & Witthaus, 2019), thereby increasing its impact on teaching in the sector. It has also had an impact at UoB, as it is included in the readings for the PGCHE [D3VII].</p> <p>Online induction for campus-based students</p> <p>While at Loughborough, I helped develop an online induction programme for campus-based first-year Business students, in order to prepare them to navigate campus, use the VLE and start building a social network before their arrival. I conducted a review of the literature (Witthaus, 2015), which helped academics in the School to create an effective online induction programme [D3VII].</p> <p>Student engagement in online learning: an evaluation</p> <p>In 2016-17, as part of my PhD, I carried out an independent, developmental evaluation of Kiron's⁵ education offer to refugees and asylum seekers (Witthaus, 2018), using the Communities of Inquiry (Col) framework, which analyses student engagement in terms of teaching presence, social presence and cognitive presence (Garrison, Anderson & Archer, 2010). The impact of this evaluation is discussed in Case Study 2. In the same study, I critiqued the Col framework, concluding that its key strength is the attention it draws to the importance of social presence as an enabler of learning, and that the framework is most useful when complemented by the notion of "learning presence" (Shea & Bidjerano, 2010).</p>	<p>K4</p> <p>K3</p> <p>K4</p> <p>K1</p> <p>K5</p> <p>K3</p>	<p>V1, V2</p> <p>V3</p> <p>V4</p> <p>V3</p> <p>V1, V2</p> <p>V3</p>
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⁵ <https://kiron.ngo/en/>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>The framework was weak in accounting for learner agency, however, and so I am currently exploring other models, including Redmond et al.'s (2018) framework, which was based on a meta-review of the recent literature. I have presented this framework to academics in several workshops (see Section A1). The inclusion of the social and emotional engagement categories are helpful in raising awareness of academics that online teaching is not just about content delivery. Early on in the Covid-19 crisis, I wrote a blog post for the Association for Learning Technology, encouraging academics to consider applying this framework (Witthaus, 2020). The post was shared by many readers on social media, and obtained the highest number of views of all blog posts ever on the ALTC website at that time [D3VII].</p> <p>“ABCD” (Activity-Based Course Design)</p> <p>I recently co-designed and facilitated a session on learning design for the HEFi Festival 2020 with a colleague. I devised the title, ‘Activity-Based Course Design’ (ABCD), to emphasise that we need to shift our culture of teaching from content delivery to designing for active learning, e.g. through problem-solving, discussion with peers and critical reflection. This session drew on and adapted existing openly-licensed, tried-and-tested resources from UCL (Young & Perović, 2016), the Open University (Galley, 2015) and the University of Leicester (Armellini & Aiyegbayo, 2010; Conole, 2014). We based the webinar around the six types of learning activities (acquisition, discussion, practice, investigation, collaboration and production) from UCL’s “ABC Learning Design” toolkit, aiming to raise academics’ awareness of enhancing the quality of their teaching through designing a range of activity types. Feedback on this session indicated that academics felt they had gained practical skills to engage their students in remote delivery [D3VII].</p> <p>In conclusion, my support for academic colleagues at UoB and beyond is substantially based on research (both my own and that of others), and I have always attempted to model a scholarly approach to teaching for others.</p> <p>Max word count: 700; Your word count: 699</p>	<p>K4</p> <p>K1, K2, K3</p> <p>K2, K3</p> <p>K1</p> <p>K6</p>	<p>V3</p> <p>V2</p> <p>V1</p> <p>V3</p> <p>V4</p> <p>V3</p>
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

	<p>learning environments. <i>Computers and Education</i>, 55(4), 1721–1731. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2010.07.017</p> <p>Witthaus, G. (2015). Findings from a desk research study into online and blended induction for students in UK universities. [Unpublished manuscript]. Academia.edu.</p> <p>Witthaus, G. (2020, March 14). When the VLE becomes your campus: Some thoughts on engaging learners online [Blog]. <i>ALTC Blog</i>. https://altc.alt.ac.uk/blog/2020/03/when-the-vle-becomes-your-campus-some-thoughts-on-engaging-learners-online/</p> <p>Witthaus, G., & Robinson, C. (2016). <i>Lecture Capture Literature Review: A review of the literature from 2012 to 2015</i>. Loughborough: Centre for Academic Practice, Loughborough University. Available at: https://www.lboro.ac.uk/services/cap/tel/tools/</p> <p>Young, C., & Perović, N. (2016). Rapid and Creative Course Design: As Easy as ABC? <i>Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences</i>, 228(June), 390–395. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.07.058</p>		
<p>TOTAL WORD COUNT FOR AREAS OF ACTIVITY:</p>	<p>Max word count: 3,500; Your word count: 3,460</p>		

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

Professional Recognition Scheme – Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Log

Name: Gabi	Surname: Witthaus
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The purpose of this form is to provide you with an opportunity to demonstrate how you engage with continuing professional development in relation to your subject / discipline and its pedagogy, as well as your skills for working with others. As such it is linked to Area of Activity A5. You may wish to make links elsewhere in your application to the professional development activities listed here but this is not required in every case. When read together with the other elements that make up your submission this log of activities should demonstrate how you make yourself a better teacher / practitioner through your engagement with continuing professional development. Max word count: 1500.

<p>Please list below 8-10 key professional development activities. These can be: formal activities such as workshop or conference attendance; work-based activities such as module design or use of technology; and informal activities such as discussions with colleagues or departmental meetings.</p> <p>When reflecting on your professional development, and where appropriate, incorporate ways in which you have co-ordinated, supported, supervised, managed and / or mentored others (colleagues/ students) in relation to teaching and learning or ways in which your engagement with CPD has informed how you undertake this activity.</p>	<p>Please provide the date of the event or activity.</p>	<p>Please explain how the activity has impacted upon your practice and professional development.</p>	<p>Indicate which dimensions of the UKPSF these activities have helped you engage with.</p>
<p>Twitter</p>	<p>Since Jan 2008</p>	<p>I have had a Twitter profile for 12 years, and have built up a diverse network of people who share my professional interests. I check Twitter</p>	<p>A5 V3, V4</p>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

		several times a week, and find it a particularly good source of information on topics that I am not actively researching myself, for example, learning analytics and decolonising the curriculum. This helps me to participate in discussions with colleagues at UoB about these matters in a more informed way than I would otherwise be able to, and to know where to look for further information when colleagues ask for my advice. My experience bears out evidence from the literature that Twitter is an effective tool for personal CPD (e.g. Emke, 2019). [117]	K4
Received coaching from a colleague at a previous institution	March to Oct 2016	I was fortunate to have the opportunity to receive six coaching sessions from a qualified coach at Loughborough University. This experience made me aware of the need to be critical of my own tendency at the time to view my role as supporting colleagues to 'fill gaps' in their knowledge and skills base. This led me to question whether I was (as I believed) truly starting from a strengths-based perspective (Buckingham & Clifton, 2001), or whether my own mid-set was more reflective of a traditional, deficit paradigm when it came to designing CPD programmes for staff. I realised that the default tendency is generally to start designing such a programme by 'identifying gaps' and then to look for resources – human or otherwise – to fill the gaps. It takes effort to resist this approach, as it is so deeply embedded in HE institutional culture. I now try to always look for opportunities to change the narrative, emphasising that any CPD initiatives should be practitioner-led, based on critical dialogue, and informed by evidence. I am deeply grateful to the colleague who coached me through this learning curve. [185]	A1, A4, A5 V1, V3
PhD: <i>Learning, Teaching and Assessment in HE</i> module	Oct 2017 to March 2018	I am currently completing my PhD in Higher Education: Research, Evaluation and Enhancement through Lancaster University. It is a structured programme – I participated in four taught modules in the first two years, and am now doing my thesis. Each of the modules has had an impact on the way I have gone about my work in supporting academics.	

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

		<p>The <i>Learning, Teaching and Assessment in HE</i> module was directly relevant to the work I do in supporting academics, as it exposed me to the wide range of literature around the scholarship of learning and teaching in HE. I used the opportunity to explore the conceptual framework of the Third Space (e.g. Potter & McDougall, 2016) in relation to educational technology and widening participation. This culminated in a book chapter (Witthaus & Ryan, 2020; 2021) on displaced people and mobile learning. My key message in this chapter, derived from Third Space theory (especially Bauhn and Fulya Tepe (2016)), was that when learners find themselves in “hybrid” cultural situations (which inevitably happens when individuals from diverse educational, cultural and geographical backgrounds come together as students in HE), this hybridity can be very productive if all individuals experience agency over their learning. I now have a better understanding of issues to consider when designing online learning for people in marginalised or low-tech communities, and have shared this learning when supporting teachers. [227]</p>	<p>A3, A4, A5 K1, K2 V3, V4 V1, V2, K3 V2 K1</p>
<p>PhD: <i>Evaluation and Enhancement in HE</i> module</p>	<p>Apr to Sept 2017</p>	<p>This module gave me a greater conceptual understanding of the need for evaluation in HE, and the relationship between evaluation and enhancement initiatives. As part of this module, I carried out an evaluation of aspects of Kiron’s online HE programmes for refugees (Witthaus, 2018), and was invited to Berlin (Dec 2017) to present my findings to Kiron staff to inform their ongoing curriculum development process. More recently, I applied my knowledge about evaluation to the HEFi Remote Teaching Resource by proposing a formal evaluation project to assess the impact of the resource over time, and helped to design the evaluation project. Alongside the aim of improving the RTR, a major intended output of this evaluation is a series of case studies based on UoB teachers who have benefited from the resource, demonstrating good bimodal teaching practice in a variety of contexts. The longer-term aim is to further inform teaching practice across the university and enhance the education experience of students. [160]</p>	<p>A5 K5, K6 V3, V4 K1, K5 K6</p>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

<p>PhD: Research component</p>	<p>Oct 2016 to present</p>	<p>The <i>Research Skills</i> module in my PhD gave me immediately usable research skills. It enhanced my skills in conducting literature reviews to inform institutional policy and practice (e.g. Witthaus & Robinson, 2016). This understanding is also valuable when working in a research-informed teaching environment, as it enables me to support academics in curriculum development where the student is framed as researcher.</p> <p>I am currently writing my thesis on online engagement in a widening participation context, which involves conducting a case study of refugees who are distance learners on a Master's programme at a UK university. From my research interviews, I am learning about the support needs of students living in marginalised or fragile contexts, and this experience has made me more deeply aware of the need for inclusive approaches to online and remote teaching. I have found the theoretical framework of the "capabilities approach" (Boni & Walker, 2013; Hart, Sarangapani & Lowe, 2012; Sen, 1995) to be very helpful as it posits that individuals have different "capabilities" of fulfilling their learning goals and aspirations, and that these varying capabilities often reflect social inequalities. In order to offer inclusive, equitable higher education, institutions and teaching staff need to be as informed as possible about their students' learning environments and avoid making assumptions.</p> <p>I now always seek opportunities to raise academics' awareness of equity issues when designing and delivering their modules. As an example, I advise academics to include students in the design of assessments (e.g. by asking students to contribute to a pool of assignment questions which is moderated by the lecturer), to ensure that the assessment remains relevant to all students. [271]</p>	<p>A5 K1, K4 V3 V3, V4 K3, K4 V2 K2 V1, V2 A3</p>
<p>Member of GO-GN (Global OER Graduate Network)⁶</p>	<p>Jan 2017 to present</p>	<p>This network of PhD students (whose research projects include a focus on open education), experts, supervisors and mentors keeps me up to</p>	<p>A4, A5</p>

⁶ <https://go-gn.net/>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

		date with developments in HE related to open educational resources and practices in HE. The benefits of open education are that it contributes to widening participation in HE, and also that it promotes better quality teaching materials due to the opportunities for public scrutiny and reiteration based on feedback received. I co-ran a HEFi showcase workshop with a copyright expert from the library in October 2019, where I shared some of this knowledge with participants who were interested in using and developing open-access teaching resources. [107]	V3, V4 V2 K1
HEFi workshop on Accessibility	6 June 2019	This workshop made me more aware of the need to embed accessibility into the design of teaching and learning resources, and gave me the rationale and the tools I needed for doing so. I was subsequently able to check the accessibility of the template I developed for CAL TALKS to ensure it meets the government's accessibility requirements ⁷ that apply to all HEIs, and to help academics ensure that their own teaching resources are accessible. Accessibility is an essential component of inclusive teaching, helping to ensure that all students can not only meet the requirements of their courses but also achieve their personal aspirations. [104]	A1, A5 K4 V1 V4 V2,
WONKHE conference: 'NO BUILDINGS FROM SEPTEMBER: What on earth do we do about the learning experience?'	7 May 2020	In the morning of this event, which focused on the transition to remote delivery during the pandemic, there were four parallel panel discussions aimed at academics and senior management members at UK HEIs in different disciplines. Afterwards, all participants were invited to contribute to a Padlet to say what their key 'takeaways' were from the parallel sessions they had attended. I subsequently analysed the Padlet, and found that, for many of the participants, the main thing they had learnt from the experts on the panels was that creating a sense of belonging online for students was critical. This is borne out by much of the literature on online engagement (e.g. Meharg, & Craighill, 2014; Wenger, 2000). Having seen how much of an impression this point made on the	A5 K1, K3 V1, V2

⁷ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2018/952/contents/made>

APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

		audience, I now give extra emphasis to it in workshops I run with academics. [142]	
LES Webinar on Inclusivity and Welfare Online	3 July 2020	This session included a presentation by two colleagues who had carried out research among students, and they found that students were hungry for interactive elements when learning remotely. This confirmed my own understanding of online engagement, providing useful anecdotal evidence I can use when talking to other academics. [48]	A5 K3, K4
UoB Online Listening Event	15 July 2020	In this event, staff from a minority ethnic background were invited to talk about their experience of working at UoB, sharing their stories about situations where they had felt excluded or undervalued. I was grateful for the opportunity to listen in on this discussion, as it raised my awareness of the prevalence of micro-aggressions towards people in racial minorities. Some of the stories shared were hard to listen to, particularly as I recognised myself as a possible culprit (for example, assuming that a person with an English sounding name will be white). It caused me to look for signs of implicit bias in my own discourse, and gave me a reference point for raising awareness of implicit bias when running workshops for academics, in order to promote an inclusive environment for teaching and learning. [134]	A5 V1, V2

TOTAL WORD COUNT FOR LOG OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES	Max word count: 1500; Your word count: 1,495
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APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

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Witthaus, G. & Ryan, G. (2021). ‘Supported mobile learning in the “Third Spaces” between formal and non-formal education for displaced people’, in J. Traxler & H. Crompton (Eds). *Critical Mobile Pedagogy: Cases of Inclusion, Development, and Empowerment* (pp. 76-88). New York: Routledge. Available at: <https://www.routledge.com/Critical-Mobile-Pedagogy-Cases-of-Digital-Technologies-and-Learners-at/Traxler-Crompton/p/book/9780367204570>

Professional Recognition Framework – Case Study
APPLICATION FOR D3 SENIOR FELLOWSHIP

Name: Gabi	Surname: Witthaus
Applying for UKPSF Descriptor	<input type="checkbox"/> Senior Fellow (D3)
<i>Submission requirements</i>	<i>Two case studies, up to 1000 words each</i>

The case studies should be drawn from recent practice and must relate to higher education learning. Case studies can take many forms, for example the exploration of the development and delivery of a sequence of teaching sessions, module or programme. They might focus on other aspects of the student experience such as induction to university, the development of distance learning approaches, inclusivity. Alternatively, they could reflect on your work in a particular role (e.g. programme leader, assessment officer) or set of experiences (e.g. mentoring, research supervision, curriculum review). Your case studies should also demonstrate an integrated approach to academic practice, where subject and pedagogic research and / or scholarship are successfully incorporated into your practice. Assessors will be looking for a sustained record of effectiveness in relation to your practice.

The case studies offer you the opportunity to reflect in depth and allow you to develop a narrative that explores what you have done, why you have done it that way, what the outcomes have been (whether for you, colleagues and / or your students) and how you have evaluated its success. There is also the opportunity, through the case studies, to think about next steps.

At least one of your case studies must draw out the way in which you have co-ordinated, supported, supervised, managed and / or mentored others in relation to teaching and learning. This relates to criteria D3.7.

You should, in addition, indicate (through annotation) where you claim engagement with any of the areas of activity, core knowledge and professional values of the UKPSF.

PLEASE NOTE: Submissions in excess of the word counts will not be reviewed and will be returned to applicants to edit. This may mean that you miss the opportunity to have your application assessed.

Case study 1: BDx, PEDL and CAL TALKS

Birmingham Digital Exchange (BDx)

BDx, an EEF-funded project, was a CPD initiative aimed at engaging UoB staff in conversation about the impact of digital technologies on learning and teaching. BDx was conceived by academic leads in MDS and CAL, and executed by the CAL DE team. Preparation for BDx had begun in 2017 prior to my arrival, and I took over its leadership in late 2018. I evaluated the materials that had been developed to date [K5], and found a substantial mismatch between the academic leads' vision statement that referred to an open-ended "conversation", and the formal course that had been produced by my team. I persuaded my colleagues that, in order to be true to the vision of the EEF proposal, we needed to build a community of practice for informal sharing of practice (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Almond, 2015; McDonald et al., 2008; Tight, 2015; Wilson, Wilson & Witthaus, 2020) [V3, V4, D3VII]. I then completely redesigned BDx [A1, A4], as a series of open-ended conversations between academics, based around a series of "hybrid" webinars (on-site gatherings which were also streamed live as webinars) [K3, K4], and eliminated the assessment tasks, as BDx was not a credential-awarding course [A3, V1]. My colleagues were persuaded by my knowledge of communities of practice, and agreed that the radical changes I had made were necessary and appropriate, and the academic leads endorsed the revised plan [D3VII].

I subsequently led the CAL DE team in delivering BDx [A2]. Over 100 academics engaged, and many indicated that they found the webinars highly engaging. Through BDx, I demonstrated that webinars could be an engaging form of staff CPD [D3VII] – a full year before the Covid-19 pandemic [K4].

Following on from BDx, a further tranche of funding was sought in order to expand the approach to UoL students in the first half of 2020. The application was successful, confirming that BDx was seen by decision-makers as having achieved its goals with academics, and that the same innovation could work with students [A1, A4, V2, D3VI]; however, it has had to be put on hold during the pandemic.

PEDL and CAL TALKS

In 2019, inspired by BDx, I initiated a CPD programme called Pedagogy for Engaging Distance Learners (PEDL) [V3] for CAL academics who teach on distance programmes [D3VII]. Academics were invited to be “discussants” at webinars [A1, K2, K3, K4], and to share resources via a dedicated Canvas module. The aim was to model good practice in online education, while also providing flexibility for time-poor academics [V1]. I led the first PEDL webinar (on online engagement) on 8th Jan 2020 [A2, K2].

When the pandemic arrived, my planning for PEDL formed the foundation for our team’s strategy to support all academics with bimodal teaching [A1, K2, K3, V3, D3VII]. Together with colleagues in the CAL HEFi team, I created a Canvas site and named it CAL TALKS (CAL Teaching, Assessment and Learning: Knowledge Sharing), signalling it as a space for practitioner-led sharing and exchange of ideas [K1, V1]. Working closely with the School Digital Education Leads and the CAL DE team, I now curate resources submitted by academics [A4] and lead drop-in sessions and webinars on teaching and learning [A2]. Where appropriate, these are recorded, edited and made available in CAL TALKS [K4].

CAL TALKS aims to enable the sharing of teaching practice [A1, K1, K2, K3] and to prompt reflection by academics on their own teaching practice in relation to the scholarship of teaching and learning (Weller, 2015) by providing links to external resources [V3]. CAL TALKS also aims to help academics meet institutional and professional body requirements, as well as government requirements e.g. by including essential information on meeting safeguarding and accessibility standards [K6, V4].

CAL TALKS does not include formal assessment of academics’ learning; however, the site includes a section on assessment and feedback, with pointers to suitable existing resources, for example the HEFi RTR, international websites such ‘Re-engineering Assessment Practices in Higher Education’ (REAP)⁸, and works by prominent authors, e.g. Bearman et al. (2016), and Zhu and Carless (2018) [A3].

Some early indicators of the impact of CAL TALKS, in the form of feedback from academics, were shared by the CAL DoE at a UEB meeting in October 2020, including the following [A1, A4, K4, D3VII]:

- “Contributing to the CAL TALKS was a great opportunity to collaborate with colleagues and work through the practicalities of how online seminars would operate ahead of time. We spotted many issues that have helped me avoid further problems now we are running these sessions for students.”

- “It’s been really helpful to be able to find out more about what other colleagues are doing in their online classes, especially since we’re not able to meet in person for chats in the corridors right now. Resources like CAL TALKS makes me feel more connected to others.”
- “I am just using CAL TALKS at the moment to prep my teaching; so, so good!! Thanks to all!”
- “CAL TALKS has really helped in building a sense of community for developing online teaching in the College.”

In conclusion, I recently initiated a dialogue with our College Academic Policy Partner (CAPP) for Registry Services about the CAL HEFi team playing a more formal role in UoB’s quality enhancement processes in future, by supporting module teams with their annual module review [D3VII]. By doing this, we will also have an indirect impact on the quality assurance of learning and teaching at UoB, i.e. the “collection of policies, procedures, systems and practices internal or external to the organisation designed to achieve, maintain and enhance quality” (the Analytic Quality Glossary, cited in Williams, 2016, p. 98). This is because the annual module review is likely to include actions taken by Schools to address important metrics for UoB’s accountability to stakeholders, including those for the TEF and the NSS [K5, K6, D3VII]. Insights gained from this process will also help to provide future direction for CAL TALKS.

Case study 1, Max word count: 1000; Your word count: 999

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Case study 2: Widening participation in HE through open online learning

In recent years, I have used research as a strategy for influencing academics and senior leadership in HE to review their open, online education offerings [V3, K5]. Many institutions offer MOOCs as a way of providing flexible learning and making HE more accessible to all. However, there are significant barriers to take-up of these opportunities, and my research aims to help universities address two of these: firstly, the difficulty for learners in getting their non-formal online learning recognised by other HEIs, and secondly, the difficulty for some learners of sustaining their online engagement [V1, V2]. The former involves a focus on quality assurance (QA), in that it highlights the need for institutions' accountability to stakeholders, and the latter on quality enhancement (QE), as it seeks to improve the student learning experience [K6]. Below, I outline my research in these two intersecting areas, my dissemination activities, and their impact.

Recognition of MOOC-based learning

I led a study into the validation of MOOC-based learning called “OpenCred” (Witthaus et al., 2016) for the EU’s Joint Research Centre. My co-researchers and I identified the key QA indicators that typically enabled non-formal, credit-bearing online courses to be recognised by other HEIs. These included: transparent statements of learning outcomes, robust assessment procedures, and alignment between outcomes, teaching and assessment [K6, V4]. Our OpenCred report also put forward a recognition model to help academics design short, online courses that would fulfill these requirements [V3, K4]. The report focused on enabling MOOC-providing HEIs to be accountable to their stakeholders, and so it was aimed primarily at senior leadership, while also providing academics with the tools and evidence to advocate for institutional policy around the recognition of prior learning of non-traditional students [V2]. The OpenCred recognition model has had wide uptake within the HE sector. Its trajectory of adoption and adaptation can be traced through the following publications which cite and build upon it: Buchem, van den Broek & Lloyd (2016); Camilleri & Rampelt (2018); Cirlan & Loukkola (2020); Harris & Wihak (2018); and Inamorato Dos Santos, Punie, & Muñoz (2016) [D3VII].

I also presented at the EMOOCS17 conference on recognition of open learning and the “unbundling” of HE [V4]. Two years later, I received the following email from a delegate:

“[A]fter a very inspiring presentation you made at the EMOOCs conference in Madrid... I shared your presentation with some colleagues, here at UCLouvain (Belgium) and we used it several times to help us think about how we want to use digital resources and transform Higher Education through online learning. We are now in a step of building an institutional strategy regarding online learning and open education. We are still inspired by your drawing/graphic ... and intend to use this graphic as a framework for reflection.” [D3VII].

Kiron - evaluation of MOOC-based provision

In March 2017, I was invited by Kiron Open Higher Education⁹ (an NGO that provides pathways for refugees globally into and through HE via MOOCs) to give a keynote address at a conference in Berlin on how the OpenCred model enabled HEIs to recognise MOOC credits [A2, A3, K1, K4, V1, V2, V4]. Subsequently, many of the participating HEIs began accepting students who had achieved MOOC credits directly into the second semester of undergraduate programmes (Rampelt & Suter, 2017), thus providing new access routes into HE for non-traditional learners [D3VII].

I later carried out an independent evaluation of Kiron’s MOOC-based provision for refugees, focusing on online learner engagement and the implications for curriculum design (Witthaus, 2018) [A1, K5, V3]. Based on in-depth interviews with learners, using the Community of Inquiry model (Garrison), I proposed guidelines for online course creators - for example, considering the different ways in which “teaching presence” can facilitate learning where there is no direct interaction between teachers and students, and demonstrating the valuable role that social presence plays in supporting cognitive engagement [K1, K2, K3, K4]. Kiron noted that my evaluation triangulated their own findings from a large-scale data analysis [V3], thus contributing to their curriculum development (Niedermeier, 2018), and influencing the learning experience of Kiron’s own 10,000+ students as well as that of other students enrolled on the online courses offered by Kiron’s 145 partner institutions worldwide [D3VII].

Nuffic - microcredentials

In March 2019, I was invited to give the keynote address for a conference in Den Haag hosted by Nuffic Netherlands, based on OpenCred and my curriculum development work with Kiron [D3VII]. The audience consisted of experts in QA (particularly credit transfer) and open educational practitioners - two professional communities that do not usually meet. Through my presentation, I helped foster communication between these two groups so that they could collaborate effectively in developing resources to help universities recognise non-formal online learning (e-Valuate, 2019a; 2019b) [D3VII].

This year, I was invited to join the Steering Committee of an EU-funded project led by Nuffic, called "STACQ: Stacking credits & the future of the qualification". My role is to support the development of an online application for the evaluation of MOOCs [K5], and to contribute to a position paper on microcredentials and the future of degrees [V4]. These outputs are likely to make a significant contribution to the sector by identifying good practice in online learning design and assessment [K2], ultimately enabling more non-traditional learners to engage and succeed in HE [K6, V1, V2, D3VII].

The above scenarios demonstrate my leadership role in advancing open online HE as a common good through effective learning design for credit recognition and student engagement. My impact is further demonstrated by the fact that I have received numerous invitations to speak to different audiences about these subjects e.g., at the Hasso Plattner Institute in Potsdam in December 2017, the SchoolNet Eminent Conference for teacher trainers in Lisbon in December 2018, and the Cross-Institutional Learning Design Network at Dublin City University in April 2019 (details available on my website¹⁰) [D3VII]. In disseminating my research to these audiences, I have aimed to foster collaboration and open sharing of evidence-based, inclusive learning design practices at every opportunity [V1, V2].

Case study 2, Max word count: 1000; Your word count: 1000

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